

Entrepreneurial Attitude of Women Students of Colleges in Puducherry

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Introduction

An entrepreneur is the one who starts his own, new small business with new ideas and works hard to take up the challenges. The motive for entrepreneurship lies in the urge to identify the sources of existing and emerging customer dissatisfaction and developing solutions to eliminate them (Ramachandran, 2003). Entrepreneurs are not simply born; they are trained and developed to undertake new ventures and be creative in their endeavours. But for that the entrepreneurs are to be equipped with the information necessary for enterprise building and must be sharpened in entrepreneurial skills. Entrepreneurial Development is designed to help the individuals in strengthening their entrepreneurial motive and in acquiring skills and capabilities necessary for playing the entrepreneurial role effectively.

The Government of India has set up three national-level Institutes for Entrepreneurial development. They are, the National Institute for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise (NI-MSME),Hyderabad; the National Institute of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development(NIESBUD) in Noida and the Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship(IIE) in Guwahati. In Puducherry, the District Industries Centre (DIC) provides a wide range of services and support to the entrepreneurs who are budding and also for the unemployed youth who can acquire skill in computer hardware and software, electrician, electronics, composing and printing, Auto mechanic, etc. So the aspiring youth regardless of gender can make use of these opportunities in developing their entrepreneurial qualities.

Women Entrepreneurship

Female feticide and discrimination no longer remains a barrier for the promising, ambitious and challenging women who had been winning the race of competitive ventures regardless of gender prone hurdles. An enterprise owned and controlled by a woman having a minimum financial interest of 51 % of the capital and at the same time giving at least 51 % of the employment which is generated in the enterprise to other women, is the basic criteria for a woman

entrepreneur. With their strong qualities, many women are in the frontline in business. Some of such successful women entrepreneurs who have proved that women can think and go beyond any kind of hurdles are viz. Dr.Kiran Mazumdar Shaw, MD of Biocon Ltd.; Indra Nooyi, CFO and President of PepsiCo.; Vandana Luthra, Founder of VLCC, a beauty and wellness giant; Ekta Kapoor, Founder of Balaji Telefilms; NainaLal Kidwai, Country Head and Group General Manager HSBC Group India; Indu Jain, Chairperson of Bennett, Coleman & Co. Ltd.; Chanda Kochar, MD & CEO of ICICI Bank; Suchi Mukherjee, Founder of Limeroad; Richa Kar, Founder of online lingerie store Zivame and Aditi Gupta, Founder of Menstrupedia. These women can very well be taken as role models by every female who aspire for heights.

Statement of the Problem

The budding women entrepreneurs need to have a reasonable level of awareness about the concept of entrepreneurship, schemes and training for developing entrepreneurial skill being offered by the Central and State governments. While the DIC offers wide opportunities for the youth who approach it, whether the women students are aware and avail the benefits had to be identified. Entrepreneurship, if chosen as a career by women may or may not affect their personal life which aspect needed to be thrown light on. To study these issues the present study has been conducted.

Objectives of the Study

Following objectives have been set for the study to explore the research problem.

1. Knowing the awareness level of the women students of colleges in Puducherry about Entrepreneurial Development and Schemes offered by government
2. Assessing the opinion of the students regarding choice of their career as entrepreneurs
3. Studying the confidence level of the students in handling entrepreneurship.

Preparedness, Awareness and Attitude towards Entrepreneurship

In order to find the preparedness, awareness level and attitude of the respondents on entrepreneurship, the questions were posed and the collected responses are given in the table below.

1. Entrepreneurship subject in Degree /Curriculum

A majority of 51 percent of the respondents responded that they did not study entrepreneurship subject in their degree/curriculum and 49 per cent of the total respondents have studied entrepreneurship subject in their degree. Hence it is concluded that a majority of 51 per cent of the respondents had entrepreneurship subject in their degree/curriculum.

Preparedness and Awareness towards Entrepreneurship

	Preparedness/ Awareness	Yes	%	No	%
a	Have you studied Entrepreneurship subject in your Degree curriculum?	49	49	51	51
b	Did you attend any Seminar, Workshop and Conference on EDP?	53	53	47	47
c	Have you undergone any training program which is conducted by DIC or Government Agencies?	17	17	83	83
d	Do you know the schemes offered to women entrepreneur?	41	41	59	59
e	Do you have any business/managerial experience?	14	14	86	86

Source: Primary data

2. Seminars, Workshop and Conference on EDP

A majority of 53 per cent of the respondents have said that they have attended Seminars, Workshop and Conference on EDP during their study and 47 percent of the respondents have not attended any Seminar, Workshop and Conference on EDP. Hence, it is concluded that a majority of 53 percentage of the respondents have an exposure to EDP as they attended Seminars, Workshop and Conference in that regard.

3. Training program conducted by DIC or Government Agencies

The training schemes especially for the self employment of women are introduced by government departments which include Support for Training and Employment Program for Women (STEP), Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), and other programmes being conducted by Small Industry Service Institutes (SISIs), State Financial Corporations, National Small Industries Corporations and District Industrial Centers (DICs).

In order to find out whether the respondents have attended any training program conducted by District Industries Center (DIC) or Government Agencies, the question was posed and the collected responses reveals that a very high majority of 83 percent have not participated in any training program organized by DIC or Government Agencies and only 17 per cent of the respondents have undergone training on EDP organized by DIC or other Government Agencies in Puducherry.

4. Awareness on Schemes offered to women Entrepreneur

Whether the women students are aware that DIC and some of the Government departments are offering training programmes and schemes for the benefit of budding entrepreneurs had been identified in this study. 59% of the respondents opined that they are not aware of the Schemes offered to women entrepreneurs by DIC and other Government departments and 41 percent of the respondents said that they are aware of such schemes. So it is evident that majority of the respondents are not aware of the facilities available for the women entrepreneurs in Puducherry.

5. Business or managerial experience

It is obvious from the collected responses that a majority of 86 percent do not have any business or managerial experience and only 14 per cent of the respondents have business or managerial experience as 78 out of 100 respondents are not from business family. Hence it is concluded that majority of the study respondents do not have business or managerial experience.

Gender Attitude towards Entrepreneurship

Attitude	Yes	%	No	%
If your carrier is a woman entrepreneur, will it affect your family life?	26	26	74	74
Will you face any specific problem being a woman to become an Entrepreneur?	43	43	57	57
Can you successfully run your enterprise without the help of male members?	62	62	38	38

Source: Primary data

6. Confidence level, preparedness and Gender attitude

In order to test the confidence level of the women students of colleges and their willingness towards entrepreneurship, three questions were posed such as

- (a) If your carrier is a woman entrepreneur, will it affect your family life?
- (b) Will you face any special problem for being a woman to become Entrepreneur?
- (c) Can you successfully run your enterprise without the help of male members?

A very surprising fact had been identified that majority of the respondents accounting to 74 percent responded that if they become entrepreneur it will not affect their family life. Only 26 percent have felt that it will affect their family life.

For the second question, majority (57%) of the students answered that just because they are women, there will not be any problem if they become entrepreneurs. Only 43% felt that they may face problems.

It is good to know that the young girl students are having much confidence to pursue their career as entrepreneur and that too without the support of men. A reasonable majority of 62 percent of the respondents have expressed that they can successfully run their enterprise without male members' help.

Chart on Preparedness, Awareness and Attitude of Students towards Entrepreneurship

T-Test Results

Opinion on Preparedness, Awareness and Attitude towards Entrepreneurship

Calculated Value	Table Value	Significance Level	Df	Type	Inference
0.1277	2.977	@1%	14 (8+8 - 2)	2 tailed probability	Significant
	2.145	@5%			

Source: Primary Data

The Student's t-Test is used to determine whether two samples are likely to have come from the same two underlying populations that have the same mean. t- Test uses the data of agreed and disagreed respondents with 'Yes' and 'No' responses to compute t-statistic. The value calculated by t-Test with two tails, has derived the probability of lesser value than table value under the "same population means". Hence probability is not associated with Student's paired t-Test, with a two-tailed distribution.

Age, Education and Community Wise Opinion on Preparedness, Awareness and Attitude Towards Entrepreneurship

CRITERIA		AGE			COMMUNITY			EDN. STATUS	
		18-21	22-25	26-30	BC	MBC	SC	UG	PG
Studied entrepreneurship in Degree curriculum	Y	12	32	5	20	18	7	11	38
	N	27	24	0	17	18	10	25	26
Attended any Seminar, Workshop on EDP	Y	23	27	3	21	17	9	19	34
	N	16	29	2	16	19	8	17	30
Undergone any training programme by DIC	Y	8	9	0	6	6	3	9	8
	N	31	47	5	31	30	14	27	56
Schemes offered to women entrepreneur	Y	19	25	5	19	21	5	18	31
	N	20	31	0	18	15	12	18	33
Have any business/managerial experience	Y	6	8	0	2	6	4	5	9
	N	33	48	5	35	30	13	31	55
Carrier is a women entrepreneur will it affect family	Y	10	16	0	10	11	4	12	14
	N	29	40	5	27	25	13	24	50
Face any special problem for being a women to become entrepreneur	Y	18	22	3	15	15	9	19	24
	N	21	34	2	22	21	8	17	40
Successfully run your enterprise without male member's help	Y	32	29	1	23	26	9	29	33
	N	7	27	4	14	10	8	7	31

Source: Primary data

Ho1 - There is no significant difference between the respondents' opinion on entrepreneurship awareness, preparedness and attitude based on their Age, Education and Community

CHI SQUARE TEST RESULTS

Demographic Factors	Calculated value	Table Value	Level of significance	D.F	Inference
Age wise	311.72	24.996	5%	15	Rejected
Education wise	22.475	24.996		15	Accepted
Community wise	14.038	38.885		26	Accepted

Source: Calculated from Primary data

The calculated value of chi square is 311.72 which is more than the table value of 24.996. @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it can be concluded that there is significant difference between the opinion on entrepreneurship preparedness, awareness and attitude based on their age.

Further, the null hypothesis is accepted for the opinion of the education wise respondents. The calculated value of chi square is 22.475 which is less than the table value 24.996 @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it

can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the opinions on entrepreneurship preparedness, awareness and attitude based on their education.

The calculated value of chi square is 14.038 which is less than the table value 38.885 @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the opinion on entrepreneurship awareness/ preparedness and their education.

Findings

- A majority of 51 per cent of the respondents studied entrepreneurship subject in their degree curriculum.
- It is found that 53 percentages of the respondents have basic knowledge / awareness on EDP by attending Seminar, Workshop and Conference on EDP.
- It is shocking to note that a very high majority of 83 percent of the respondents have not participated in any training programme organized by DIC or Government Agencies and only 17 per cent of the respondents have undergone such training on EDP.
- It is found that a majority of 59 per cent of the respondents are not aware of the schemes offered by DIC and government departments to Entrepreneurs.
- It is unfortunate to note that a very high majority of 78 % of the study respondents do not have any business or managerial experience.
- A surprising result has been found that the young women girl students are having much confidence and a majority of 62 percent of the respondents have expressed that they can successfully run their enterprise without male member's help.
- The value calculated by t-Test with two tails, has derived the probability of lesser value than table value under the "same population means". Hence probability is not associated with a Student's paired t-Test, with a two-tailed distribution.
- Chi square analysis Results: The calculated value of chi square is 311.72 which is more than the table value of 24.996 @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it can be concluded that there is significant difference between the opinion on entrepreneurship awareness/ preparedness and their age.
- The null hypothesis is accepted with the demographic factors of education and their community. The calculated value of chi square is 22.475 which is less than the table value 24.996 @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. . Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the opinion on entrepreneurship awareness/ preparedness and their education.
- The calculated value of chi square is 14.038 which is less than the table value 38.885 @ 5 % level of significance with 15 degree of freedom. . Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the opinion on entrepreneurship awareness, preparedness and attitude based on their community.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurs, to become successful in business should articulate the vision and objectives so as to build up self confidence in pursuing their career. Many new, budding entrepreneurs get locked in a stage where they face hurdles and that would make them shift their career which is not advisable as in present day's condition self-employment is better than bending to some masters for earning. To avoid such ends and to handle the contingencies in doing business, they need to gain adequate knowledge and exposure from EDP related seminars and conferences. It is because; focused initiatives with preplanned objectives and a support of adequate training would definitely

create promising entrepreneurs. But their preparedness, awareness and attitude count a lot in their initiative as entrepreneur. Only such people can shine as good leaders also which is an inevitable role in the course of entrepreneurship.

The findings of this study on “Entrepreneurial Attitude of Women Students of Colleges in Puducherry” indicates that 83% of the sample respondents have not attended any training programme organized by Government agencies and 59 % are not even aware of the Entrepreneurship schemes offered by these departments for women. This state should change which is possible if they are given awareness to these aspects in their colleges or by media and guided to approach the right departments for further guidance. And it is good to know that 57 % of the women students are very confident that just because they are women, they will not face any problem if they become entrepreneurs and 62 % expressed that they can successfully run their enterprise without male members’ help. In future, the number of women who feel so should increase and they should recognize the fact that they can prove their best if they themselves come forward with full of confidence.

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